

Together,
there's
something
science
can do.

Issue Tracker 2025/004 April 23, 2025

Pharma companies expected to absorb any tariff hit in short term: The Trump administration has initiated a national security investigation into pharmaceuticals to justify the need for tariffs aimed at boosting domestic US manufacturing. The specifics regarding the rates and timing of these tariffs remain uncertain. While tariffs would likely not affect the cost of brand name drugs in the short term, generic drugs could see higher prices almost immediately because of their lower profit margins.

Pharma companies collaborate on secure data sharing for AI: Researchers at UCB published a proposal to federate data for AI-assisted drug discovery – called Federated Learning using Information Distillation (FLuID) – to overcome inequalities of data availability between models. Instead of sharing data, individual private models annotate a shared public dataset, with annotations shared with other models instead of the data itself. This approach allows for collaboration between private machine learning models while maintaining data privacy.

Simon Fraser University Implements Open Scholarship University-Wide: Simon Fraser University (SFU) became the first Canadian university to adopt a university-wide open scholarship framework. Under the initiative, which will be implemented over the next three years, all university researchers are encouraged to make their data, publications and intellectual property freely available to other academics. With a \$1 million endowment from the Tanenbaum Open Science Institute, SFU will develop platforms to organize and facilitate the sharing of information with the international academic community.

Pharmaceutical industry worries about FDA delays: Due to widespread layoffs at the FDA as part of the Trump administration's cuts to the broader federal public service, the agency is planning for fewer food and drug inspections. While delays in inspections and approvals have not yet materialized, they represent a serious threat to the approval timelines for new drugs and treatments, which could harm profitability and patient outcomes.